

Growth and yield response of improved and traditional rice varieties to N fertilization at various growth stages

S. Singh, Central Agricultural Research Institute, Port Blair 744101, India

Growth and yield response of rice varieties to N fertilization depend to a great extent on growth duration, plant type, and growth stage when N is applied. To determine the most responsive growth stage to N fertilization in both improved and traditional rice varieties, we conducted a pot experiment during the wet season with two distinct rice varieties—Mansarover (semitall, high-yielding, improved) and C14-8 (tall, lodging-susceptible, low-yielding, traditional).

Thirty-day-old seedlings of both varieties were transplanted in cement pots (30 × 30 × 30 cm) prefertilized with a full dose of P and K (40 kg ha⁻¹ each). The planted pots of both varieties were divided into seven treatments each: (T1) control (no N applied), (T2) low N

(100 kg ha⁻¹) at active tillering (15 d after planting [DAP]), (T3) high N (200 kg ha⁻¹) at active tillering, (T4) low N at panicle initiation (PI), (T5) high N at PI, (T6) low N at 50% flowering, and (T7) high N at flowering. All treatments had five replications. A full dose of N (100 and 200 kg ha⁻¹) was applied only once at the respective growth stages. Plants were sampled at 50% flowering to record growth parameters such as leaf area per plant and specific leaf weight; growth and yield attributes were recorded at maturity.

Mansarover showed maximum growth and yield response to N applied at the vegetative growth stage (active tillering), followed by N applied at PI, but did not respond to N applied at flowering. C14-8, however, recorded the highest growth and yield responses to N applied at PI followed by N applied at flowering, but showed a nonsignificant response to N applied at active tillering (see table).

Irrespective of variety and growth stage, application of a high N level brought about greater leaf area

expansion and lower specific leaf weight than a low N level. The high grain yield of rice varieties recorded under different treatments was mainly attributed to a greater leaf surface and more panicles plant⁻¹ and grains panicle⁻¹. The growth and yield responses of both rice varieties were invariably higher under high N level than under low N level. N application reduced harvest index in C14-8, which had a lower harvest index and produced more dry matter than Mansarover (see table).

The differential growth and yield responses of modern and traditional rice varieties to N fertilization in stages may perhaps be due to their distinct growth and phenological characteristics. The greater response of traditional tall late-duration variety C14-8 to late N fertilization was mainly due to the significant increase in panicle-bearing nodal tillers, whereas Mansarover failed to retain its panicle number with late N application.

Nitrogen fertilization at various growth stages did not show much

Effect of N fertilization at various growth stages on growth and yield parameters of rice varieties, Port Blair, India.

Treatment ^a / variety	Plant height (cm)	Leaf area plant ⁻¹ (cm)	Leaf area tiller ⁻¹ (cm)	Specific leaf weight (mg cm ⁻²)	Days to maturity	Panicles pot ⁻¹ (no.)	Grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	1,000- grain weight (g)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Economic yield (g pot ⁻¹)	Biologi- cal yield (g pot ⁻¹)	Harvest index (%)
<i>Mansarover</i>												
T1 Control (no N)	98	13.9	107	5.6	140	11	86	25.7	21.8	20.5	44.1	46
T2 - N1 at T	114	40.6	150	6.0	145	23	101	25.2	13.3	58.5	124.5	47
T3 - N2 at T	115	45.3	181	5.9	147	28	89	24.6	27.0	61.3	138.0	44
T4 - N1 at PI	100	29.1	145	6.1	140	24	69	23.2	23.5	37.0	74.0	50
T5 - N2 at PI	97	39.0	152	5.5	140	31	64	23.0	40.7	45.6	95.0	48
T6 - N1 at F	98	20.0	118	5.5	140	10	87	20.6	21.0	22.0	42.0	52
T7 - N2 at F	98	24.0	126	5.4	140	13	88	21.0	16.0	24.0	52.0	46
Mean	102	30.3	139	5.7	142	20	83	23.5	23.3	38.4	81.4	47
<i>C14-8</i>												
T1 - Control (no N)	140	12.7	115	6.7	175	10	91	25.0	17.5	20.8	52.3	40
T2 - N1 at T	155	24.8	146	6.1	175	20	64	27.2	13.5	34.7	126.0	28
T3 - N2 at T	159	39.0	150	5.7	174	23	97	25.4	24.5	53.5	189.6	28
T4 - N1 at PI	148	28.8	144	6.1	195	15	106	26.0	18.8	41.7	133.4	32
T5 - N2 at PI	148	46.4	186	5.6	195	31	83	25.0	19.8	61.5	182.6	34
T6 - N1 at F	143	31.2	142	6.9	185	21	94	25.8	26.5	47.2	145.1	33
T7 - N2 at F	142	58.8	195	5.9	185	30	82	24.0	20.8	55.0	170.5	32
Mean	148	34.5	159	6.1	183	21	88	25.5	20.2	45.0	142.7	32
LSD (5%)												
Variety	4.3	0.6	8	ns	7	2.0	7.0	ns	ns	4.4	8.4	2.7
Treatment	8.0	4.5	10	ns	5	3.8	13.0	ns	6.0	8.2	15.7	5.0
V x T	11.0	6.8	13	ns	12	5.4	18.2	ns	8.4	11.7	21.2	7.1

^aN1 = low N (100 kg ha⁻¹); N2 = high N (200 kg ha⁻¹), T = tillering, PI = panicle initiation, F = flowering.

impact on days to maturity in Mansarover, but showed a marked effect on maturity period in C14-8 when applied at later growth stages, mainly because of a delay in maturity

of nodal panicles. It is clear from the results that active tillering was the most N-responsive growth stage in high-yielding Mansarover, whereas the

reproductive and flowering stages were found to be the most N-effective growth stages in traditional variety C14-8. ■

Crop management

Lock-lodge technology for rice ratooning

R. Mohan, L. Aruna, J. Ram Mohan, and R. Poonguzhalan, Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru College of Agriculture and Research Institute, Karaikal 609603, India

Ratooning of rice could be an important crop establishment alternative in many agroecosystems. But low yield potential and asynchronous grain ripening constrain the widescale use of ratooning in the tropics. Braiding and lodging (lock-lodge method) the stubbles after harvest of the main crop can overcome these limitations considerably.

We tested the ratoon performance of varieties IR20, ADT38, CO 43, and Ponni in an experiment conducted at

Grain yield and duration of main and ratoon rice varieties.

Variety	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)			Duration (d)		
	Conventional ratoon	Lock-lodge ratoon	Main crop	Conventional ratoon	Lock-lodge ratoon	Main crop
IR20	1.4 (41.1)	2.9 (82.7)	3.5	62	95	117
CO 43	1.7 (38.9)	3.1 (70.8)	4.4	97	97	140
ADT38	1.3 (23.7)	3.0 (55.2)	5.4	79	105	133
Ponni	1.5 (26.1)	2.4 (41.2)	5.9	71	97	140

Numbers in parentheses indicate the percentage grain yield when compared with the respective main crop.

Tamil Nadu Agricultural University in Coimbatore in 1993-94 using both conventional and lock-lodge methods of ratooning. Results showed that lock-lodge ratooning consistently out-yielded the conventional method irrespective of variety. All the traits of the ratoon crop measured were significantly better in the lock-lodge

ratoon crop. Grain yield of lock-lodge ratoon crop increased by 41.2% for Ponni to 82.7% for IR20 compared with their respective main crop (see table). Growth duration of lock-lodge ratoon ranged from 95 to 105 d, whereas that of conventional ratoon ranged from 62 to 97 d depending on variety. ■

Disease management

Soil-borne and seed-borne pathogens of rice in rice - wheat system-based farmers' fields in Uttar Pradesh

A. Kumar, G.B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology (GBPUAT), Pantnagar 263145, Uttar Pradesh, India; L. Willocquet and S. Savary, IIRI-ORSTOM Project on Rice Pest Characterization, IIRI; and U.S. Singh, GBPUAT

Pests (insects, weeds, pathogens) are an important component for sustaining rice - wheat systems. Among them, soil- and seed-borne pathogens may play a specific role. Cropping practices may affect the dynamics of these pathogens, both in their survival and epidemic phases. More specifically, the carryover role of other crops in rotation with rice may be critical for these

diseases. Pathogen interactions may also alter disease patterns in a field. These interactions remain largely unknown, and we report here some preliminary results on this topic.

Disease incidence due to a few soil- and seed-borne pathogens was quantified in farmers' fields for sheath blight (ShB, *Rhizoctonia solani*), stem rot (SR, *Sclerotium oryzae*), brown spot (BS, *Cochliobolus miyabeanus*), sheath rot (ShR, *Sarocladium oryzae*), panicle blast (PB, *Pyricularia grisea*), crown sheath rot (CShR, *Gaeumannomyces graminis*), and false smut (FS, *Ustilaginoidea virens*). These diseases can be transmitted by seeds (BS, ShR, PB, CShR) or survive as propagules in the soil or in plant debris (ShB, SR, BS, PB, CShR, FS) (Ou 1985). Glume discoloration (GD) symptoms were also considered because they are

associated with the presence of different fungi, such as *P. grisea* and *C. miyabeanus*. Eight fields selected to represent a range of crops preceding rice were assessed: two with wheat (B3 and B6), one with rice (B4), one with sorghum (B1), one with maize (PP5), one with lentil (B9), one with fallow (PP2), and one with mint (PP3).

Diseases were assessed at the milk stage. In each field, 20 hills were sampled following a zigzag pattern. For each hill, the total number of tillers; number of tillers infected by ShB, SR, BS, and CShR; total number of panicles; number of panicles infected by ShR, PB, and FS; and number of panicles showing GD were recorded. Sheath blight, stem rot, brown spot, glume discoloration, and sheath rot were consistently observed in all eight